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A GAUSSIAN MIXTURE MODEL BASED SPEECH RECOGNITION SYSTEM USING MATLAB

Manan Vyas

B.E Electronics, University of Mumbai

ABSTRACT

This paper aims at development and performance analysis of a speaker dependent speech recognition system using MATLAB®. The issues that were considered are 1) Can Matlab, be effectively used to complete the aforementioned task, 2) Accuracy of the Gaussian Mixture Model used for parametric modelling, 3) Performance analysis of the system, 4) Performance of the Gaussian Mixture Model as a parametric modelling technique as compared to other modelling technique and 5) Can a Matlab® based Speech recognition system be ported to a real world environment for recording and performing complex voice commands. The aforementioned system is designed to recognize isolated utterances of digits 0-9. The system is developed such that it can easily be extended to multisyllabic words as well.

KEYWORDS

Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), Feature Extraction, Fast Fourier transform, Discrete Cosine Transform, Linear Prediction (LPC), Mel Frequency Cepstral Co-efficient (MFCC), Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM).

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AUTHOR

Manan Vyas received his Bachelor of Engineering in Electronics degree from University of Mumbai in July 2012. He has also completed MITx 6.002 – a pilot course on Circuits and Electronics by Massachusetts Institute of Technology with an A grade. He is also a recipient of the J.R.D Tata Scholarship for excellent academics during his engineering. His passions include playing football and trekking.

TWO NEW APPROACHES FOR SECURED IMAGE STEGANOGRAPHY USING CRYPTOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUES AND TYPE CONVERSIONS

Sujay Narayana¹ and Gaurav Prasad²

¹Department of Electronics and Communication, NITK, Surathkal, INDIA

²Department of Information Technology, NITK, Surathkal, INDIA

ABSTRACT

The science of securing a data by encryption is Cryptography whereas the method of hiding secret messages in other messages is Steganography, so that the secret's very existence is concealed. The term 'Steganography' describes the method of hiding cognitive content in another medium to avoid detection by the intruders. This paper introduces two new methods wherein cryptography and steganography are combined to encrypt the data as well as to hide the encrypted data in another medium so the fact that a message being sent is concealed. One of the methods shows how to secure the image by converting it into cipher text by S-DES algorithm using a secret key and conceal this text in another image by steganographic method. Another method shows a new way of hiding an image in another image by encrypting the image directly by S-DES algorithm using a key image and the data obtained is concealed in another image. The proposed method prevents the possibilities of steganalysis also.

KEYWORDS

Steganography, Cryptography, image hiding, least-significant bit (LSB) method

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AUTHORS

Sujay Narayana received the BE degree in Electronics and Communication from KVG College of Engineering, Sullia, in 2009. He is currently with the Department of Electronics and Communication, National Institute of Technology Karnataka, Surathkal.

Gaurav Prasad received the BE degree in Information Science from P.A College of Engineering, Nadupadavu, Mangalore in 2006 and MTech degree in Information Security from NITK, Surathkal . He is currently with the Department of Information Technology, National Institute of Technology Karnataka, Surathkal.

CONTENT BASED IMAGE RETRIEVAL USING COLOR AND TEXTURE

Manimala Singha and K.Hemachandran

Dept. of Computer Science, Assam University, Silchar India. Pin code 788011

ABSTRACT

The increased need of content based image retrieval technique can be found in a number of different domains such as Data Mining, Education, Medical Imaging, Crime Prevention, Weather forecasting, Remote Sensing and Management of Earth Resources. This paper presents the content based image retrieval, using features like texture and color, called WBCHIR (Wavelet Based Color Histogram Image Retrieval).The texture and color features are extracted through wavelet transformation and color histogram and the combination of these features is robust to scaling and translation of objects in an image. The proposed system has demonstrated a promising and faster retrieval method on a WANG image database containing 1000 general-purpose color images. The performance has been evaluated by comparing with the existing systems in the literature.

KEYWORDS

Image Retrieval, Color Histogram, Color Spaces, Quantization, Similarity Matching, Haar Wavelet, Precision and Recall.

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AUTHORS

Ms. Manimala Singha received her B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in Computer Science from Assam University, Silchar in 2005 and 2007 respectively. Presently she is working, for her Ph.D., as a Research Scholar and her area of interest includes image segmentation, feature extraction, and image searching in large databases

Prof. K. Hemachandran is associated with the Dept. of Computer Science, Assam University, Silchar, since 1998. He obtained his M.Sc. Degree from Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati and M.Tech. and Ph.D. Degrees from Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad. His areas of research interest are Image Processing, Software Engineering and Distributed Computing.

ADVANCES IN AUTOMATIC TUBERCULOSIS DETECTION IN CHEST X-RAY IMAGES

Wai Yan Nyein Naing, Zaw Z. Htike

Department of Mechatronics Engineering Faculty of Engineering, IIUM, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB) is very dangerous and rapidly spread disease in the world. In the investigating cases for suspected tuberculosis (TB), chest radiography is not only the key techniques of diagnosis based on the medical imaging but also the diagnostic radiology. So, Computer aided diagnosis (CAD) has been popular and many researchers are interested in this research areas and different approaches have been proposed for the TB detection and lung decease classification. In this paper, the medical background history of TB decease in chest X-rays and a survey of the various approaches in TB detection and classification are presented. The literature in the related methods is surveyed papers in this research area until now 2014.

KEYWORDS

CAD, Tuberculosis, Image processing, Radiographs

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF VOWELS, DIPHTHONGS AND GLIDES OF SINDHI

Ayaz Keerio¹, Lachhman Das Dhomeja², Asad Ali Shaikh², Yasir Arfat Malkani¹

¹Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

²Institute of Information and Communication Technology, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

ABSTRACT

Sindhi language is primarily spoken in the Sindh province of Pakistan, and in some parts of India. Languages phonemic inventory include vowels, consonants and diphthongs. This paper presents acoustic analysis and properties of the glide consonants of Sindhi. Glides are considered having stable and predictable formant structure and associated acoustic properties like vowels and diphthongs. Understanding the corresponding acoustic similarities, differences and relationship between three types of these sounds is the subject of discussion of this paper.

KEYWORDS

Consonants, Formant frequencies, Glides, Phonemic inventory, Sindhi

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AUTHORS

Dr. Ayaz Keerio is an assistant Professor at the Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science (IMCS), University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan. He got his Master's degree in Computer Science from University of Sindh, Jamshoro (Pakistan) and PhD from University of Sussex, UK in 2011. His main area of research is Speech Recognition and Synthesis systems. He is also interested in digital signal processing, Data communication & networks and mobile & distributed computing systems.

Dr. Lachhman Das Dhomeja is an Assistant Professor at the Institute of Information & Communication Technology (IICT), University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan. He got his Master's degree in Computer Technology from University of Sindh, Jamshoro (Pakistan) in 1991 and PhD from University of Sussex, UK in 2011. His main research area is Pervasive Computing in general and policy-based context-awareness in particular. His other research interests include secure device pairing in ubiquitous environments, Data communication & networks, software architectures and Distributed Computing.

Dr. Asad Ali Shaikh is an Associate Professor and director of the Institute of Information and Communication Technology (IICT), University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan. He did his Masters degree in Computers Engineering from Clarkson University, USA in 1991 and PhD degree in Information Technology from University of Sindh, Pakistan in 2006. His current research focus is on the protocol design, security issues in computer networks and software development. He is also interested in digital signal processing and Data communication & networks.

Dr. Yasir Arfat Malkani is a Lecturer at the Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science (IMCS), University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan. He got his Master's degree in Computer Science from University of Sindh, Jamshoro (Pakistan) in 2003 and PhD from University of Sussex, Brighton, UK in 2011. His main area of research is Pervasive Computing. His research is focused on secure device/service discovery and access control mechanisms using policies and location/proximity data/information. He is also interested in sensor networks, wireless networks (including WiFi, Bluetooth, WiMAX, etc), and solutions to various issues in distributed and pervasive computing systems through the integration of tools and techniques from distinct disciplines/areas. He is also interested in the design and/or development of various tools and techniques that might be useful in giving world-wide recognition to various national languages, such as SINDH and URDU.

A PAPER ON AUTOMATIC FABRICS FAULT PROCESSING USING IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUE IN MATLAB

R.Thilepa

Department of EEE Adhiyamaan Educational & Research Institute, Hosur-Tamil nadu 635 109

M.Thanikachalam

Department of Civil Engineering, Velammal Engineering College, Chennai-600 066

ABSTRACT

The main objective of this paper is to elaborate how defective fabric parts can be processed using Matlab with image processing techniques. In developing countries like India especially in Tamilnadu, Tirupur the Knitwear capital of the country in three decades yields a major income for the country. The city also employs either directly or indirectly more than 3 lakhs of people and earns almost an income of 12, 000 crores per annum for the country in past three decades [2]. To upgrade this process the fabrics when processed in textiles the fault present on the fabrics can be identified using Matlab with Image processing techniques. This image processing technique is done using Matlab 7.3 and for the taken image, Noise Filtering, Histogram and Thresholding techniques are applied for the image and the output is obtained in this paper. This research thus implements a textile defect detector with system vision methodology in image processing.

Keywords:

Image processing, Matlab 7.3, Gray image, Histogram, Thresholding.

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AN ACTIVE CONTOUR FOR RANGE IMAGE SEGMENTATION

Khaldi Amine¹ and Merouani Hayet Farida²

¹Department of computer sciences, Badji Mokhtar University, Laboratory of LRI BP12.Sidi Amar, 23000 Annaba, Algeria

²Department of computer sciences, Badji Mokhtar University, Laboratory of LRI BP12.Sidi Amar, 23000 Annaba, Algeria

ABSTRACT

In this paper a new classification of range image segmentation method is proposed according to the criterion of homogeneity which obeys the segmentation, then, a deformable model-type active contour “Snake” is applied to segment range images.

KEYWORDS

Image segmentation, Active contour, Snake, Range image, Classification, Criterion of homogeneity.

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FUSION OF FINGERPRINT AND AGE BIOMETRIC FOR GENDER CLASSIFICATION USING FREQUENCY AND TEXTURE ANALYSIS

S. S. Gornale* and Kruthi R[#]

*School of Mathematics and Computer Science, Department of Computer Science, Rani Channamma University, Belagavi-Karnataka-INDIA.

[#]Research Student, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Jain University, Bangalore-Karnataka-INDIA

ABSTRACT

Classification of gender from fingerprints is one of the important steps in forensic anthropology. This forensic anthropology is used to identify the gender of a criminal in order to minimize the suspects list of search. A very few researcher have worked on gender classification using fingerprints and have gain the competitive results. In this work we are trying to fuse the fingerprint and age biometrics for gender classification. The real fingerprints were collected from different age groups such as 15-20 years and 20-60 years of the rural and urban people. According to this experimental observation soft biometric information can be used significantly to improve the recognition performance of biometric system. The overall performance of the proposed method is found to be satisfactory and more competitive.

KEYWORDS

Gender classification, frequency domain, texture analysis, soft biometrics and hard biometrics traits.

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TEST DATA COMPRESSION BASED ON GOLOMB CODING AND TWO-VALUE GOLOMB CODING

Priyanka Kalode¹ and Mrs. Richa Khandelwal²

¹Department of Electronics Engineering, Ramdeobaba college of Engg and Mgt, Nagpur

²Department of Electronics Engineering, Ramdeobaba college of Engg and Mgt, Nagpur

ABSTRACT:

In this paper, we discuss test data compression and decompression method based on variable length Golomb codes and 2-V Golomb Codes for test data. The method is targeted to minimize the amount of test data, which reduces the size of memory required in ATE for test data and also time required to transfer test data to specific device on SOC. We completed MATLAB coding for both methods and applied test vectors of some standard ISCAS benchmark circuits and compared results for same. Experimental results on ISCAS benchmark circuits show that the compressed data produced by 2-V Golomb coding is better than Golomb Coding method.

KEYWORDS:

Automatic test equipment (ATE), precomputed test sets, variable-to-variable-length codes, Golomb coding, RLE, SOC, Golomb Coding, 2-V Golomb Coding.

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A REVIEW PAPER: NOISE MODELS IN DIGITAL IMAGE PROCESSING

Ajay Kumar Boyat¹ and Brijendra Kumar Joshi²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Electronics Telecomm and Computer Engineering, Military College of Tele Communication Engineering, Military Head Quartar of War (MHOW), Ministry of Defence, Govt. of India, India

²Professor, Department of Electronics Telecomm and Computer Engineering, Military College of Tele Communication Engineering, Military Head Quartar of War (MHOW), Ministry of Defence, Govt. of India, India

ABSTRACT

Noise is always presents in digital images during image acquisition, coding, transmission, and processing steps. Noise is very difficult to remove it from the digital images without the prior knowledge of noise model. That is why, review of noise models are essential in the study of image denoising techniques. In this paper, we express a brief overview of various noise models. These noise models can be selected by analysis of their origin. In this way, we present a complete and quantitative analysis of noise models available in digital images.

KEYWORDS

Noise model, Probability density function, Power spectral density (PDF), Digital images.

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